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The end of "modernity": reductionist Protestant digitality as the root of the big tech madness

„The worldlessness that began with the modern era is indeed unparalleled. What has taken the place of the world is consciousness, accessible only to self-reflection, in whose field the highest activity is the play of formulas of the intellect and the most intense experience is the desires, the sensations of pleasure and displeasure, which, being physical in nature, behave 'irrationally' because they cannot be dealt with by rational arguments, i.e., cannot be reckoned with, and are therefore considered passions. Thus, this entire inner life ultimately fell apart into a rational-calculative activity of the intellect and an irrational-passionate emotional life, and this division, which tore the inner human being apart, was as unbridgeable as Descartes' subject-object division.“ (Hannah Arendt)¹

The discrepancy between the challenges of global climate change and actions aimed at providing ever-increasing amounts of energy for the operation of enormous data centers for AI applications, regardless of the ecological costs, characterizes the phenomenon of "world loss" as a sign of decline in the modern era, which is coming to an end.

The basis of the "truth regime" of modernity is classical logic with its principle of "tertium non datur." The reductive exclusion of the "third" enables clear judgments and linear cause-and-effect concepts. The principle of the excluded third "establishes" the symbolic sphere of rational and symbolic human thought, whose evolutionary genesis is closely linked to the ability to speak.

The "modern" regime of truth is based on the assumption that the complexity of the "world" can be broken down into sub-problems through the application of rational conclusions and thus transformed into conscious knowledge. The "world" is "describable" as "reality"; it can be converted into a symbolic representation. This

¹ „Die Weltlosigkeit, die mit der Neuzeit einsetzt, ist in der Tat ohnegleichen. Was in ihr an die Stelle der Welt getreten ist, ist das nur der Selbstreflexion zugängliche Bewußtsein, in dessen Felde die höchste Tätigkeit das Formenspiel des Verstandes ist und die intensivste Erfahrung die Begierden, die Lust- und Unlustempfindungen sind, die, körperlicher Natur, sich ‚irrationally‘ gebärden, weil man ihnen mit Vernunftgründen nicht beikommen, d. h. nicht mit ihnen rechnen kann, und die daher für Leidenschaften gehalten werden. So fiel schließlich dieses ganze Innenleben in eine rational-rechnerische Verstandestätigkeit und ein irrational-leidenschaftliches Gefühlsleben auseinander und diese Spaltung, die den inneren Menschen auseinanderriß, war so wenig überbrückbar wie die Subjekt-Objekt-Spaltung des Descartes.“ Arendt (1996): Vita activa oder Vom tätigen Leben. 8. Aufl. München: Piper, S. 312 f.

concept corresponds to the principle of "digitality" = the representability of "reality" through its conversion into distinct symbols, into "data".

In 1932, quantum theory brought about the collapse of modernity's regime of truth: John von Neumann published his fundamental statement that it was pointless to attempt to trace the entire complexity of physical processes from the observed world to the world of the observer.² This destroyed the foundations of modernity's regime of truth based on rational "digital" realism: from then on, rational thinking was no longer "automatically" grounded in "reality," but its "truth" was limited solely to the network of statements within a "floating" symbol system—the semiosphere. In such a "de-grounded" symbol system, it is the actor with the most manipulative resources who determines what is considered true.

Simone Weil, sister of the famous mathematician André Weil, felt directly affected by this event. She expressed her view of quantum physics in the following sentence:

„It is this contradiction that is expressed in the concept of quanta or energy atoms ... and which, since 1900, has robbed science of the significance it had enjoyed for four centuries, without anyone being able to give it any other.“³ Jürg Fröhlich (ETH Zurich) writes that Simone Weil "reflected on the problems of modern mathematics and physics with impressive intuition."

In a very telling footnote, Hannah Arendt refers to Simone Weil's quantum-physical "primordial shock," citing a text published under the pseudonym "Emil Novis" in Simone Weil's Cahiers du Sud (December 1942). In this text, Weil deals with the effects of the quantum-theoretical rupture of the modern regime of truth:

„Something infinitely more precious than science itself is compromised in this crisis: the notion of truth, which the 18th century and especially the 19th century very closely linked to science, quite wrongly, but we have retained this habit. The disappearance of scientific truth has made truth itself disappear in our eyes, accustomed as we are to taking one for the other. As soon as truth disappears, utility immediately takes its place, for man always directs his efforts toward some good. But intelligence no longer has the power to define or judge this utility; it only has the license to serve it. From arbiter, it becomes servant, and desires give it orders. Moreover, public opinion becomes the sovereign master of thoughts instead of conscience, for man always submits his

² von Neumann (1932) Mathematische Grundlagen der Quantenmechanik: Die Grundlehren der mathematischen Wissenschaften in Einzeldarstellungen, S. 223 f.

³ »C'est cette contradiction qui apparaît dans l'idée de quanta ou d'atomes d'énergie ... qui a ôté à la science, à partir de 1900, la signification qu'elle avait eue au cours de quatre siècles sans qu'on ait pu lui en donner aucune autre.« (Cited from [Fröhlich \(2011\) Bemerkungen zum Weltbild der Physik des 20. Jahrhunderts](#), S. 5).

thoughts to a higher control, whether in value or in power. That is where we are today. Everything is geared toward usefulness, without any thought of defining it; public opinion reigns supreme, in the village of scholars as in the great nations. We seem to have returned to the era of Protagoras and the Sophists, a time when the art of persuasion—whose modern equivalents include slogans, advertising, propaganda through public meetings, newspapers, cinema, and radio—took the place of thought, determined the fate of cities, and brought about coups d'état. Thus, Book IX of Plato's Republic seems to describe contemporary events. But today it is not Greece that is at stake, it is the entire globe. And we lack Socrates, Plato, Eudoxus, the Pythagorean tradition, and the teaching of the Mysteries. We have the Christian tradition, but it can do nothing for us until it comes alive in us again.*⁴

Arendt writes about Weil's attempt to save the modern regime of truth: „*Simone Weil points out at length how something ‚infiniment plus précieux‘ than science is compromised in this crisis, namely, the notion of truth; she fails, however, to see that the greatest perplexity in this state of affairs arises from the undeniable fact that these hypotheses ‚work.*“⁵

The extent to which the new scientific hypotheses "worked" became suddenly clear to skeptical contemporaries after the first nuclear explosion, if not before. Now they suddenly realized which side of the cognitive barrier between language and "truth" they were on. In response to the existential shock and the accompanying end of an era, the "right" sought refuge in their retro-utopias, while the Marxist "left," due to their teleological view of history inherited from Hegel — in contrast to Simone Weil — apparently did not even notice the epochal break.

This touches on one of the fundamental problems of so-called "artificial intelligence," the "grounding problem": How do you connect a symbolic system to the "world"? Large

⁴»Quelque chose d'infiniment plus précieux que la science même est compromis dans cette crise; c'est la notion de vérité, que le XVIII^e siècle et surtout le XIX^e ont très étroitement liée à la science; bien à tort, mais nous avons conservé cette habitude. La disparition de la vérité scientifique a fait disparaître à nos yeux la vérité elle-même, accoutumés que nous sommes à prendre l'une pour l'autre. Dès que la vérité disparaît, l'utilité aussitôt prend sa place, car toujours l'homme dirige son effort vers quelque bien. Mais cette utilité, l'intelligence n'a plus alors qualité pour la définir ni pour en juger, elle a seulement licence de la servir. D'arbitre elle devient servante, et les désirs lui donnent des ordres. De plus l'opinion publique devient maîtresse souveraine des pensées au lieu de la conscience, car toujours l'homme soumet ses pensées à un contrôle supérieur, soit en valeur, soit en puissance. Nous en sommes là aujourd'hui. Tout est tourné vers l'utile, sans qu'on songe à le définir ; l'opinion publique règne souverainement, dans le village des savants comme dans les grandes nations. Nous sommes comme revenus à l'époque de Protagoras et des sophistes, l'époque où l'art de persuader, dont les slogans, la publicité, la propagande par réunions publiques, journal, cinéma, radio, constituent l'équivalent moderne, tenait lieu de pensée, réglait le sort des villes, accomplissait les coups d'Etat. Aussi le IX* livre de la République de Platon semble-t-il décrire les faits contemporains. Mais ce n'est pas aujourd'hui la Grèce, c'est le globe terrestre qui est en jeu. Et il nous manque Socrate, Platon, Eudoxe, la tradition pythagoricienne, l'enseignement des Mystères. Nous avons la tradition chrétienne, mais elle ne peut rien pour nous tant qu'elle n'est pas redevenue vivante en nous.« Weil, Simone: [Réflexions à propos de la théorie des quanta](#). Veröffentlicht unter dem Pseudonym Emile Novis, in: Cahiers du Sud (1942) H. 29. S. 102–119, S. 118

⁵ Arendt (1958/1998) „The Human Condition“, S. 288, FN 53.

language models generate artificial semiospheres. However, since these machine semiospheres are "ungrounded," spectacular errors occur time and again when algorithmic-rational, generative methods are applied. Apparently, "artificial intelligence" has significant deficits in the area of "truthfulness".

This raises the question of what constitutes the basis of human "truthfulness." The modern European worldview sought the answer in the supposedly "reality-revealing" claim of rational thinking. However, according to von Neumann's formulation, this assumption was no longer tenable. How, then, does human thinking achieve "grounding"?

One solution is offered by the approach of the American polymath Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914). Peirce recognized that every distinction has a "determinant of the distinction" that is absolutely different from that which it "distinguishes". From the recognition of this general ternary nature, Peirce derived three fundamental "universes of experience": "the universe of firstness": the experience of surprise; "the universe of secondness": the experience of opposition; and "the universe of thirdness" ... which is somewhat more complicated to explain. Peirce himself found this example, among others: *„Very well. It is highly proper that Secondness should be searched to its very bottom. Thus only can the indispensableness and irreducibility of thirdness be made out, although for him who has the mind to grasp it, it is sufficient to say that no branching of a line can result from putting one line on the end of another“*⁶

With the "ternary nature" of his "semiotics," Peirce connected with the ternary intellectual culture of the so-called "Middle Ages," whose significant intellectual principle was the Trinity. Since Peirce's "rediscovery" of the ternary principle, ternary approaches have proven extremely successful in the field of scientific modeling. Quantum theoretical findings can also be modeled ternary, while "digital" representation fails due to the uncertainty of quantum physics. Ternary models are therefore more "truthful" than digital paradigms. This is not surprising, since the "digital" model is derived from the ternary model through the "tertium non datur" reduction.

Looking at European history from the perspective of its relation to truth reveals an intriguing shift from the classical narrative of progress told by modern historiography: the "ternary" epoch of the so-called "Middle Ages" represents a peak in "truth aptitude" that has not been reached again since, either in antiquity or in modern times. This superior "truth regime" led to the rich flowering of medieval intellectualism, which found its expression in the Gothic period.

A central concern of the author's cultural-historical research (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13749000](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13749000) / DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14634266](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14634266)) is to highlight the fact that Protestantism failed in its task of transforming the ternary worldview of pre-modern Europe into the modern era. The Protestant Enlightenment can be interpreted as the last

⁶ L 463: [Letter to Lady Welby](#) (12.10.04).

attempt to date to intellectually connect with medieval ternary thinking. When Hegel's enormous undertaking to conceive a modern ternary regime of truth foundered, he left behind a landscape of ruins in which "truth" became a product of political manipulation. The project of the "Enlightenment" had failed.

This "politicization" of truth took place through the degeneration of the third element into the modern concept of the "middle." This marked the transition from a relational to a substantial ontology: While in the relational-triadic paradigm, the ambivalent role of the "third"—which simultaneously creates relationships and distinctions—is understood as a prerequisite for a relationship and its defining characteristic, the substantial ontological interpretation of the "third" as the "middle" emphasizes its "identity-creating centrality." The "substance" of the "center" defines the identity of the " margins." Whoever substantially "dominates" the "center" determines what makes the difference. This degeneration of the relational-ontological concept of the "third" into the substance-ontological principle of the "center" had serious consequences. It formed the epistemic basis for the emergence of the "friend-foe" principle of modern identity formation, the "right-left" principle as the core of modern political thought, and the "purity concept" of modern racism and anti-Semitism, according to which peoples supposedly have their own genetic and cultural-geographical "center" in which all identity characteristics are substantially potentiated. The rise of the toxic "center" concept in Germany can be clearly traced through the development of the term "Mitteldeutschland" (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7434435](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434435)).

From the perspective of "truth aptitude", the modern era no longer appears progressive in comparison to the pre-modern era, but rather as an intellectual decline. Its catastrophic failure in the "loss of the world," a process of latent, systemically conditioned violent events, can be traced back to the "modern" regime of truth of a reductionist digitality. The mutilation of the triad is repeated in every modern excess of violent reduction of complexity. It constitutes the bloody matrix of modernity.

Against this backdrop, authoritarian US big tech capitalism can be described as a Protestant and post-Protestant phenomenon and a consequence of the failure of the Protestant Enlightenment to transform the ternary regime of truth from the pre-modern era to the modern era.

Europe now faces the decision of whether to follow the post-Protestant empire of the USA in its authoritarian-digital decline, or to take up the challenge of completing the Enlightenment and taking the step towards a renewed, ternary regime of truth based on fuzziness, which is compatible with the intellectual quality of the pre-modern era. Charles Sanders Peirce did the necessary connecting work that Hegel was unable to do. His triadic semiotics has long formed the solid foundation for successful triadic modeling in the natural sciences.

“You never change things by fighting the existing reality. To change something, build a new model that makes the existing model obsolete.” (Buckminster Fuller)⁷

Entwurfsskizze zu einer Semio-Cultural Grounding Theory (SCGT)

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Based on Peirce's semiotics, the SCGT develops a theoretical concept for "grounding" as a semi-cultural practice.

Modernisierung und Widerstand

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Overcoming the "Trinitarian challenge" can be described as the central hurdle of the Protestant German Enlightenment: Are Christianity and its central dogma—the Trinity—still suitable as the fundament of a "modern" state?

Weltverlust als Epochenproblem

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The essay explores the loss of human sovereignty over language as a consequence of the failed reformation of Trinitarian concepts in the "Western modern era."

⁷ Cited from Sieden (2011) A Fuller View: Buckminster Fuller's Vision of Hope and Abundance for All, Divine Arts Media, S. 358